

Learning Workshops for Local Energy Transitions: Fostering Co-Operation and New Perspectives in Rural Municipalities

Lüder, Catharina^a; Hülle, Anna^b; Nagy, Emilia^a

^aCenter for Technology and Society, Technical University Berlin

^bEnergieavantgarde Anhalt e.V.

Abstract

The article reflects on the outcome of a series of learning workshops aimed at fostering co-operation and exchange between municipal stakeholders in form of a community of practice (CoP) and identifying practical measures for local energy transitions to achieve affordable and clean energy and improve community sustainability. Participants took part in three workshops to address energy challenges, develop transformation pathways and discuss tailored strategies. The impact of the workshop series was explored through qualitative interviews with four participants and implications for the design of such formats were derived. Although the workshops did not establish a lasting CoP, they did inspire new perspectives and approaches. Municipalities recognised the potential of inter-municipal co-operation and adopted more strategic approaches to energy issues. At the same time, the workshops influenced the way participants think about existing local potential and opened up new ways of developing sustainable and resilient energy pathways in their community. The results underline the relevance of structured and methodically supported learning formats to support municipalities in making progress towards a sustainable energy transition despite governance and resource limitations.

Background of the Study/Research Project

The practice-oriented research project "Participation in the digitalised energy system through social innovations" (PaDiSo, 2022 - 2024) investigated the variety of social innovations within the energy system. It sought to identify the factors that facilitate the emergence and integration of these innovations. The project aimed to deepen the understanding of the social aspects of energy system transformation and to empower different stakeholders to actively influence this process. PaDiSo had several key objectives: to showcase different types of social innovations in the German energy transition landscape, to identify factors that

either promote or hinder the development of these innovations, to analyse how social innovations spread and are implemented in relation to existing actors and structures, and to foster regional learning processes to enable all energy system stakeholders to contribute to its transformation. Grants - Issued by Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (FKZ: 03EI5224A). <https://www.soziale-innovationen-projekt.de/>

Societal Impacts

In this short article, we describe learning workshops that were designed to bring together rural municipalities that have not sufficiently made use of their renewable energy (RE) potentials yet. The three consecutive learning workshops took place between autumn 2022 and summer 2023 as part of the transdisciplinary research project *PaDiSo*. The project elaborated a knowledge base by scrutinising institutional work of social innovation actors (Rohde et al., 2024) as well as infrastructuring processes in multi-actor co-operation (Lüder et al., in review). In addition to these research goals, the learning workshops were developed as a transdisciplinary integration format addressing the following key objectives:

1. Establish a Community of Practice (CoP) (Wenger, 1998) that would initiate communication and personal relationships between mayors and administrative staff from authorities and utilities in neighbouring municipalities.
2. Gain insights into the day-to-day challenges of implementing energy transitions in municipalities by jointly identifying and developing practical measures towards affordable and clean energy (SDG 7) for more sustainable local communities (SDG 11) in small municipalities.

In this article, we first elaborate the current situation of the German energy transition. Secondly, we describe the methods of the learning workshop format and the impact assessment one year later. Thirdly, we present the results and implications.

Over the past four years, Germany has intensified efforts to transition its energy system towards RE. This has among others led to rural areas being confronted with changing (energy) landscapes around them. Despite ongoing conflicts involving foremostly wind parks, a recent representative study (AEE, 2024) found general attitude towards energy transition to be influenced by the very presence of RE: People who already have experience with RE in their neighbourhood seem to agree considerably more to building new RE plants in their

vicinity than people who have not yet been confronted with RE, the study shows. Municipalities with few or no RE sites in their area are therefore unlikely to start their energy transition with the unquestioning approval of their citizens.

Another influencing factor for the relation between RE, citizens and municipalities was the energy crisis inflicted by the Russian war on Ukraine and the end of gas supply from Russia. Faced with soaring energy prices, citizens of the participating municipalities demanded that their mayors come up with solutions to high energy prices.

The mayors who participated in the learning workshops saw this situation as both a challenge and an opportunity. Switching to RE and building a local grid, for example, was suddenly a viable option to discuss in municipal councils and in meetings with citizens. However, the transition to decentralised RE is difficult for small municipalities because they lack structures and resources, such as staff, funding and administrative structures responsible for energy-related matters.

In the majority of small municipalities, energy is one topic among numerous mayors and administrative staff have to deal with. They struggle to build up new expertise in-between their everyday tasks. The participating municipalities expressed a desire to exchange ideas with neighbouring municipalities and share expertise to address this challenge. Still, inter-municipal exchange formats have not been widespread to date. With the learning workshops we envisaged to fill this gap. Building on this context, we designed a methodology that consisted of three consecutive learning workshops, which are described in detail below.

Methodology

Methodology of the learning workshops

Using a transdisciplinary approach (Lang et al., 2012), we co-designed the methodology in partnership between academia and practice. We aimed to tailor the learning workshops to the needs of the municipalities so that they could integrate as much insights as possible into their work. The partnership between researchers and a locally embedded intermediary, the NGO Energieavantgarde Anhalt, was central to this approach, to have up-to-date knowledge about the participants' situation at hand available for the context-sensitive preparation and reflection of the workshops.

First Learning Workshop. In an open session, regional stakeholders introduced themselves, shared their municipal challenges, and outlined their options for action and potential solutions. We clustered the inputs for group work that followed in the second half of the workshop. Tandems that complemented each other in their potentials and challenges were matched in a market place format. This setup aimed to foster co-operation and the pursuit of shared solutions even beyond the workshop. In line with the workshops' objective to promote the formation of a CoP we encouraged participants to stay in contact.

Second Learning Workshop. Applying the Theory of Change approach (Dhillon & Vaca, 2018; Schäfer et al., 2024), the participants first developed a shared vision to guide the development of strategies for municipalities to achieve greater sovereignty in their energy supply. For that they differentiated the desired changes across three spheres of descending influence (Belcher et al., 2020) guided by the following questions:

- What can *you* do about the current challenges? Which activities will directly lead to the desired effects? (sphere of control)
- What should *others* do? How can they be reached and persuaded to act in the spirit of transformation? (sphere of influence)
- What *framework conditions* (e.g. artefacts, technological innovations, regulations or services) should be in place, which you can't directly influence? (sphere of interest)

With a focus on the sphere of control, the participants defined several short-term transformation goals and described activities for prompt implementation. The workshop concluded with a reflection on the visualised transformation pathways, which informed a discussion on addressing the sphere of influence and the framework conditions. This discussion, in turn, led the research team to draft a set of key questions for decision-making processes related to local energy transformations.

Third learning workshop. Participants validated and revised the set of key questions for practicality and relevance. Through a moderated group discussion and co-writing approach, we finalised the set during the workshop. The final version is intended to facilitate municipal decision-making and the preparation of measures. In this way, the key questions should make local energy transitions more feasible for municipalities. The set is openly available on the Energieavantgarde Anhalt website.

Methodology of the evaluation

Our evaluation of the learning workshops was guided by the question: What new combinations of thinking, acting, and organising energy have emerged from the workshops? To answer this, we conducted interviews with four participants who attended at least two workshops, approximately one year after the final workshop in late summer 2024. The four semi-structured online interviews lasted about one hour each. The audio files were automatically transcribed using the Software noScribe. The transcripts were analysed following a summarising qualitative content analysis (Mayring, 2022) using QCAmap. The resulting categories were discussed and revised in two research workshops.

Results and Implications

(Inter)municipal co-operation to address resource restraints

Municipalities often lack resources for energy transitions, but improved ways of internal and external co-operation can help address this challenge. Interviewees highlighted the importance of internal co-operation, such as between mayors and heads of building authorities. However, time constraints often prevent them from attending external workshops together. The set of key questions developed in the third learning workshop provides a solution, making workshop insights and results accessible to personnel at a later date and to those who were not present. By serving as a shared repertoire of artefacts, these key questions can support a CoP (Wenger, 2000) and undergird internal co-operation.

External co-operation, such as inter-municipal co-operation, is a second strategy that municipalities use to deal with resource constraints. However, external connections between small municipalities often remain informal, with mayors and administrative staff occasionally meeting at regional training events or round tables. Energy-related issues are often discussed informally on an ad hoc basis at these meetings, which serve as a dialogue on current issues and possible solutions. To build on these existing networks, we invited municipalities from one region to participate in our learning workshops, and asked participants to bring a neighbouring municipality to the second workshop. By providing a dedicated space for energy discussions, we aimed to spark further professional exchange on this topic. Although the workshops were successful in establishing connections between municipalities, the lack of a follow-up coordination role has limited the perpetuation of these

connections beyond the workshops organised by PaDiSo. This highlights the ongoing challenge of resource constraints in sustaining inter-municipal co-operation and dialogue.

The formation of a CoP around a specific issue requires more than just a temporary structure. It also needs a certain level of institutional background and formalisation. As Wenger (1998) notes, CoPs can have an informal fabric, but in the context of our project, a more formalised approach to energy as an administrative topic would have been necessary to consolidate a CoP. The interviewees suggested that the third workshop could have been used to establish a coordination role to facilitate ongoing meetings and dialogue. This suggestion highlights the need for a more structured approach to supporting inter-municipal co-operation and dialogue.

Despite the challenges in establishing a CoP, the learning workshop format still had a number of benefits. It strengthened the idea of inter-municipal dialogue among the participants and paved the way for more interaction and relationships between the participating municipalities. The experience gained from the format was incorporated into the municipality's work and policy development, and the interactive method encouraged new ways of thinking about energy transition opportunities. Additionally, the participants reported a change in their roles and perspectives, which led to a shift in their approach to energy transition in their own municipalities. In addition to the benefits of inter-municipal co-operation, the learning workshops also had a positive impact on the participants' understanding of energy issues, as will be discussed in the following subsection.

Change of roles opens up perspectives

Many small German municipalities face significant challenges, including a shortage of skilled labour and a disproportionate number of old inhabitants. These challenges can make transitions difficult, and participants in our study, mostly mayors and building department heads, reported feeling caught between the expectations of citizens, local businesses, and the municipal council. This can lead to role conflicts and make it difficult for them to navigate their tasks.

In their daily work, the participants need to be knowledgeable and persuasive, often acting as mediators or informing others about framework conditions. In the learning workshops, however, they were able to take on the role of learners, which created a space for reflection on energy issues that are often kept in the background, such as the potential for regional

value creation. By changing roles, the participants were able to adopt new perspectives and learn something new. For example, one head of a building office reported that the way the workshops were facilitated had inspired his team leadership strategy. This was an impact that was not, and could not have been, planned for in advance by the research team.

The learning workshops also provided a platform for participants to share and discuss concrete, locally tried and tested approaches to energy issues. Without providing ready-made general solutions, the participants were able to learn from each other's experiences and adapt them to their own contexts. This approach allowed for a more nuanced and context-specific understanding of energy issues, and helped to build a sense of community and co-operation among the participants.

Implications

The interviews showed that although the learning workshops did not have the intended outcome of initiating a CoP, the participants gained new perspectives on a pressing issue. They gained new ideas on how to deal with cross-cutting energy issues by changing their view on inter-municipal co-operation to see the potential and benefits of working together. This may lead to long-term benefits as participants also developed a more strategic view of energy issues, facilitated by the transformation pathways. The strategic view puts them in a more confident position when negotiating with renewable energy project developers. As a result, the learning workshops have inspired new ways of thinking in the participating municipalities, which can form the basis for building new relationships that support energy transitions. Ultimately, the findings of our evaluation highlight the importance of supporting inter-municipal co-operation for energy transitions in small municipalities. However, consolidating these relationships requires a stable foundation and ongoing commitment.

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